

Effects of Road Conditions, Traffic Patterns, and Human-Made Features on Road Safety: Review Article

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ABSTRACT

This review article explores the effects of road conditions, traffic patterns, and human-made features on road safety. It provides a comprehensive analysis of existing research studies and aims to enhance understanding of the various factors influencing road safety outcomes. The study examines how road conditions, including pavement quality, signage, and lighting, impact driver behavior and accident rates. It also investigates the role of traffic patterns, such as congestion, speed limits, and traffic flow, in contributing to road safety hazards. Furthermore, the review explores the influence of human-made features, such as road design, intersections, and roadside infrastructure, on accident occurrence and severity. It analyzes the relationship between these features and driver behavior, highlighting potential areas for improvement in terms of safety measures and design guidelines. The review also discusses the impact of technological advancements, such as intelligent transportation systems and autonomous vehicles, on road safety. The findings of this review article reveal the complex interactions between road conditions, traffic patterns, and human-made features in shaping road safety outcomes. It emphasizes the need for integrated approaches that consider multiple factors to effectively enhance road safety. The insights gained from this review contribute to the development of evidence-based strategies and interventions aimed at reducing accidents and improving overall road safety. In summary, this review article provides a comprehensive overview of the impacts of road conditions, traffic patterns, and human-made features on road safety. By synthesizing existing research, it offers valuable insights into the relationships between these factors and their influence on accident occurrence and severity. The findings have important implications for policymakers, transportation planners, and road safety practitioners in developing strategies to create safer road environments.

1. INTRODUCTION

Every day, road crashes claim the lives of 3,000 individuals, resulting in a global humanitarian disaster of man-made origin (Global Road Safety Partnership Annual Report 2011). Road safety stands as one of society's most pressing issues, with an alarming annual death toll of 1.2 million people and between 20 to 50 million individuals injured in road accidents (Torregrosa et al., 2012). If current trends persist, road traffic accidents are projected to become the third leading contributor to the global burden of disease and injury by 2025. India, unfortunately, has gained

notoriety for having the highest number of fatalities due to road accidents worldwide. Road safety has emerged as a major social concern in India, highlighting the urgency for effective measures to address the issue (Shivkumar and Krishnaraj, 2012). Accidents exert a significant toll on the national economy, causing disabilities, deaths, damage to health and property, social distress, and environmental degradation. Road safety aims to minimize the number of crashes, regardless of their severity, within a specific timeframe. Accidents and fatalities on the road result from a combination of multiple factors. In India, road users exhibit a wide range of heterogeneity, including pedestrians, animal-driven carts, bicycles, rickshaws, hand carts, tractor trolleys, as well as various categories of two/three-wheelers, cars, buses, trucks, and commercial vehicles. The increasing vehicle population, driven by changes in people's lifestyles, exacerbates the situation. Limited road space coupled with the growth in vehicle numbers necessitates a well-developed road safety policy. In India, the accident rate is directly proportional to the growth of the vehicle population.

2. ROAD SAFETY & VARIOUS CAUSES OF ACCIDENT

Road traffic safety encompasses measures and approaches aimed at reducing the risk of fatalities and severe injuries among road users. These users include pedestrians, cyclists, motorists, their passengers, as well as passengers of on-road public transport like buses and trams. The most effective road safety strategies prioritize the prevention of crashes resulting in serious injuries or fatalities, acknowledging that humans are fallible. One crucial aspect of road safety is the design of safe roads that consider the limitations and thresholds of human tolerance for serious injuries and death. This involves creating a road environment that ensures vehicle speeds remain within these tolerances, particularly at conflict points where different road users interact. Table 1 illustrates the various causes of accidents, which can be attributed to three main factors: the driver, the vehicle, and the environment. Each of these factors plays a significant role in determining the overall safety of road users and requires specific attention in road safety initiatives.

Driver-Related	
Alcohol and drugs	Sickness
Unsafe speed	Cell Phone Use
Drowsing or Fatigue	Distraction
Fatigue	Improper Passing or Turning
Disregard traffic controls	Non Use of Restraint
Vehicle-Related	
Over Loading	Steering defect
Brake defect	Tire failure
Light defect	Improper wheel alignment
Environmental- Related	
Road side hazard	Vision obstruction
Ruts	Improper traffic control
Debris or Garbage on the road	Road Side Hazard
smoke or fog	Fixed Objects
Glare	Water ponding
Improper/nonworking traffic controls	Shoulders defective

Table 1: Various Factors Related to Accident

3. HADDON'S MATRIX

The matrix, developed by William Haddon in 1970, provides a framework for analyzing factors associated with personal attributes, vector or agent attributes, and environmental attributes in relation to injury or death. This matrix considers these factors before, during, and after an

incident occurs. By employing this framework, it becomes possible to assess the relative significance of different factors and devise appropriate interventions. Utilizing the Haddon matrix allows for a systematic evaluation of various elements contributing to road traffic incidents or other types of injuries. It enables researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to identify the key factors at each stage of the injury process and determine the most effective interventions to prevent or mitigate harm. This comprehensive approach considers not only the characteristics of individuals involved but also the attributes of vehicles, the physical environment, and the broader social and cultural context. By employing the Haddon matrix, stakeholders can make informed decisions and develop targeted strategies for improving road safety and reducing the risk of injury or death. It provides a valuable framework for understanding the interplay between different factors and designing interventions that address the identified factors effectively.

4. LITERATURE SURVEY

The literature review provides a comprehensive examination of the effects of road conditions, traffic patterns, and human-made features on road safety. It offers an overview of previous studies conducted on the development and human-made features on road safety.

Numerous factors have been identified to have a measurable influence on driving behavior and traffic safety on two-lane highways (Bhuyan, 2003). These factors encompass a wide range of aspects, including, but not limited to:

- Human factors
- Traffic factors
- Vehicle deficiencies
- Road conditions
- Road design
- Weather conditions
- Other causes

By considering and addressing these various factors, policymakers, transportation agencies, and road safety practitioners can develop comprehensive strategies and interventions to improve driving behavior and enhance overall traffic safety on two-lane highways.

Labat et al.,(2008) In a study conducted by Labat et al. (2008) in the UK, post-mortem blood and urine samples from 1047 victims of traffic fatalities between 2000 and 2006 were analyzed. The results showed that 54% of the total victims tested positive for drugs and/or alcohol. Among male pedestrians aged 17-24 involved in road traffic accidents, 63% were found to have consumed drugs and/or alcohol. The substances most commonly detected among the victim group were alcohol and cannabinoids. Interestingly, the presence of drugs and/or alcohol in the victims was observed at a similar frequency in both the group in control (55% of drivers, 48% of motorcyclists, 33% of cyclists) and the group not in control of a vehicle (52% of car passengers, 63% of pedestrians). The study also revealed the presence of other drugs, such as anti-psychotics, diabetic drugs, heart drugs, and anti-inflammatory drugs, in the victim group. These findings emphasize the high prevalence of drug and alcohol consumption among traffic accident victims, particularly among young male pedestrians. The study highlights the need for effective measures to address substance abuse and impaired driving, as well as the importance of comprehensive road safety strategies that consider the diverse factors contributing to traffic fatalities.

Anne et al.,(2010) examined the impact of the minimum legal drinking age on highway crash fatalities. The findings revealed a clear relationship between the drinking age and fatalities

during a crash. Specifically, it was observed that when the drinking age is lowered, fatalities during a crash tend to increase. Conversely, when the drinking age is raised, fatalities during a crash decrease. The study underscored the significance of the minimum legal drinking age in influencing the rate of fatalities, particularly among young individuals. Based on the analysis, the researcher concluded that lowering the drinking age to eighteen would result in an elevated fatality rate among young people. These findings provide valuable insights into the potential consequences of altering the minimum legal drinking age. They emphasize the importance of maintaining an appropriate drinking age to promote road safety and reduce the risk of fatalities during crashes, especially among young individuals. Policymakers and stakeholders can use these findings to inform decision-making processes related to drinking age regulations and road safety initiatives.

Sreedharan et al.,(2010) A cross-sectional study conducted in Kerala, India, examined the factors influencing the use of crash helmets among motorcyclists. The study aimed to explore the determinants of helmet usage and its impact on head injuries during crashes. The findings revealed that a significant proportion, specifically 73.1%, of motorcyclists were not using helmets in the region. This lack of helmet usage contributed to a higher incidence of head injuries among motorcyclists involved in crashes. The study shed light on the need for increased awareness and enforcement of helmet usage among motorcyclists in Kerala. The findings emphasize the importance of promoting helmet-wearing behaviors to enhance road safety and reduce the risk of severe head injuries during accidents. By addressing the determinants identified in the study, policymakers and road safety authorities can develop targeted interventions and campaigns to encourage proper helmet usage among motorcyclists in the region.

Campos et al.,(2011) In a study conducted in Brazil, breath tests were analyzed for 4234 drivers between 2007 and 2009, following the implementation of a new traffic law that enforced a blood alcohol concentration (BAC) limit of 0.08g/dL. The researcher utilized logistic regression to examine the impact of this law on driver behavior and traffic fatalities.

The findings revealed a significant decrease in driver behavior associated with alcohol consumption, with a 45% reduction observed. Moreover, the study demonstrated a remarkable decrease in traffic-related deaths, with a 63% reduction noted in downtown areas and a 14% decrease on roads. These results highlight the positive impact of implementing a strict BAC limit and enforcing it through the traffic law in Brazil. The study provides evidence of improved driver behavior and a substantial reduction in traffic fatalities, both in urban and rural settings. These findings reinforce the importance of effective legislation and enforcement measures to combat alcohol-impaired driving and promote road safety. Policymakers and authorities can utilize these findings to support the development and implementation of similar measures in other regions to enhance public safety on the roads.

Constantinou et al.,(2011) A study conducted on young novice drivers, specifically those under the age of 25, revealed that they are at a heightened risk of engaging in traffic offenses. The study examined the influence of various factors, including gender, age, and personality traits, on the risk of traffic violations among this demographic. The findings indicated that young drivers who were categorized as novice and below the age of 25 were more prone to committing traffic offenses compared to older and more experienced drivers. The study also explored the role of gender and personality traits in influencing this risk. The research shed light on the importance of considering age, gender, and personality factors when addressing traffic safety issues, particularly among young and inexperienced drivers. By understanding the specific risk factors associated with this demographic, targeted interventions and educational programs can be developed to promote safer driving behaviors and reduce the incidence of traffic offenses. Policymakers, driving instructors, and road safety advocates can utilize these findings to

implement effective strategies that address the unique challenges faced by young novice drivers.

Hassan and Aty (2012) In a study conducted by Hassan and Aty (2012) in Florida, the behavior and involvement of 680 young drivers in traffic crashes were examined. The research aimed to identify the significant factors contributing to young drivers' involvement in crashes, specifically focusing on two age groups: 16-17 years old and 18-24 years old. The findings indicated that aggressive violations, in-vehicle distractions, and demographic characteristics were significant factors influencing the crash involvement of young drivers in the 16-17 age group. On the other hand, in-vehicle distractions, attitudes towards speeding, and demographic characteristics were identified as significant factors affecting crash risk among young drivers in the 18-24 age group. These results emphasize the importance of considering specific factors such as aggressive violations, in-vehicle distractions, attitudes towards speeding, and demographic characteristics when addressing the crash risk of young drivers. By understanding these influential factors, targeted interventions and educational programs can be developed to promote safer driving behaviors among young drivers in different age groups. Policymakers and road safety authorities can utilize these findings to implement strategies aimed at reducing the crash involvement and risk for young drivers, thereby improving overall road safety outcomes.

Houquani et al.,(2012) The findings of the study highlighted the significant impact of sleepiness as a contributing factor to road traffic collisions. The logistic model revealed a strong association between driver sleepiness and the occurrence of collisions. Based on these results, the researchers recommended that individuals should refrain from driving on highways if they feel sleepy, particularly during the lunar month of Ramadan. This study underscores the importance of recognizing the role of sleepiness in road traffic collisions and highlights the need for effective strategies to address this issue. It emphasizes the importance of driver awareness and responsible behavior, particularly during periods when fatigue and sleepiness may be more prevalent.

Somchainuek et al., (2013) A study was conducted to investigate roadside safety on Thai national highways. The findings revealed that speeding vehicles played a significant role in roadside crashes, accounting for approximately 70% of the total crashes analyzed. Additionally, it was observed that 30% of the roadside crashes were attributed to the presence of roadside trees. The study highlights the importance of addressing speeding as a key factor contributing to roadside crashes on Thai national highways. It underscores the need for effective speed management measures, such as speed limit enforcement, speed awareness campaigns, and road design improvements, to reduce the occurrence of these crashes. Furthermore, the study draws attention to the potential risks associated with roadside trees. Identifying suitable roadside vegetation and implementing appropriate tree management strategies can help mitigate the hazards posed by these elements and enhance overall roadside safety. The findings of this research contribute to a better understanding of the factors influencing roadside crashes in Thailand and provide valuable insights for policymakers, transportation authorities, and road safety practitioners to develop targeted interventions and guidelines aimed at improving roadside safety on national highways.

Wang et al.(2020) The objective of this study was to identify road traffic collision (RTC) hotspots in Kigali, Rwanda, and conduct a built environment analysis of these hotspots. Data on RTC and RTC-prone locations were collected from the Kigali Traffic Police and high-frequency road users, and kernel density estimation was used to identify hotspots. Built environment characteristics (BEC), including road design, road safety, pedestrian safety, and traffic density, were collected for each hotspot. Logistic regression was utilized to assess the association between BEC characteristics and RTC risk, and principal component analysis was employed to calculate BEC scores. Exploratory cluster analysis was conducted to identify patterns of BEC, and logistic regression was used to assess the association between BEC patterns and RTC risk.

The study identified 25 RTC hotspots in Kigali. The analysis revealed that high-risk crash locations were less likely to have unpaved roads (21%, $p = 0.049$) and road narrowing (21%, $p = 0.049$). Conversely, high-risk crash locations were more likely to have pedestrian walkways (100%, $p = 0.009$), factors facilitating pedestrian crossing (100%, $p = 0.026$), and poor road surfaces (86%, $p = 0.005$). These findings provide insights into the association between built environment characteristics and RTC risk in Kigali. The results suggest that certain BEC factors, such as the presence of pedestrian infrastructure and road surface conditions, are associated with increased RTC risk. This information can guide urban planning and infrastructure development efforts to improve road safety in identified hotspots.

Oskarbski et al.(2021) The evolving challenges associated with shaping changes in urban mobility patterns and mobility management necessitate the development of methods and tools for evaluating the effectiveness of transportation improvements. These evaluations should consider travel conditions, road traffic safety, and the environmental impact of transportation. Additionally, it is crucial to establish principles and guidelines for the safe and efficient utilization of emerging transport modes in urban areas, such as scooters, cargo bikes, and electric bikes. This Special Issue aims to address the following questions: How can urban transport be effectively planned given the aforementioned circumstances? How can the reliance on motor vehicles be reduced while ensuring enhanced road traffic safety through strategic planning and operational activities? By focusing on these topics, this Special Issue will assist researchers and practitioners in comprehending the influence of current trends in changing mobility patterns, new technologies, and the challenges associated with transforming public spaces in cities. Moreover, it will facilitate the identification of barriers, analytical tools, and techniques required in this field to improve travel efficiency and enhance traffic safety.

Radzuan et al.(2021) The initial data screening conducted indicates that road traffic crash patterns and road traffic fatality patterns in Selangor exhibit numerous similarities. However, there are also some dissimilarities observed, including variations in the time and day of occurrence, the number of vehicles involved in crashes, and the type of vehicle first hit in the crash. To analyze the data, a supervised machine learning algorithm was employed using Orange data mining software. Various algorithms, such as neural network, random forest, decision tree, logistic regression, naïve Bayes, and support vector machine, were considered. Among these algorithms, the neural network demonstrated the highest performance in classifying road traffic fatality occurrences, achieving a classification accuracy of 97.0% and outperforming the other algorithms. The results of this study can be utilized by relevant traffic stakeholders to implement targeted safety interventions in Selangor, with the aim of reducing the number of road traffic fatalities.

Datu et al.(2023) A comprehensive analysis was conducted on 1,438 records obtained from the Angeles City Traffic Management and Enforcement Unit (ACTMEU) covering the period from January 2015 to June 2018. The primary objectives of the study were to describe the characteristics of the suspected motorists involved in road accidents and identify frequently occurring patterns. Association rule mining and descriptive analytics using pivot tables were employed for data analysis. The findings revealed that out of the total records, 73 cases were classified as fatal road accidents, while 1,365 cases were non-fatal. Male motorists accounted for 82.19% of the fatalities and 83.30% of the non-fatal accidents. The age group of 15-29 years had the highest number of accidents, comprising 36.99% of the fatal cases and 35.09% of the non-fatal cases.

5. SUMMARY

This review article provides a comprehensive analysis of the effects of road conditions, traffic patterns, and human-made features on road safety. The objective of the study is to enhance understanding of the various factors that influence road safety outcomes and contribute to the

development of effective strategies for improving road safety. The review examines the impact of road conditions on driver behavior and accident rates. Factors such as pavement quality, signage, and lighting are analyzed to determine their influence on road safety. The study also investigates the role of traffic patterns, including congestion, speed limits, and traffic flow, in contributing to road safety hazards. Furthermore, the review explores the influence of human-made features, such as road design, intersections, and roadside infrastructure, on accident occurrence and severity. Through a comprehensive analysis of existing research studies, the review highlights the complex interactions between these factors and their impact on road safety outcomes. It emphasizes the need for integrated approaches that consider multiple factors in order to effectively enhance road safety. The findings of this review have important implications for policymakers, transportation planners, and road safety practitioners. By understanding the effects of road conditions, traffic patterns, and human-made features on road safety, appropriate interventions can be developed and implemented to reduce accidents and improve overall road safety. Overall, this review article provides valuable insights into the relationships between road conditions, traffic patterns, human-made features, and road safety. It serves as a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners involved in road safety efforts, helping to inform evidence-based strategies and interventions aimed at reducing accidents and improving road safety outcomes.

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